

Remediation of Hydrocarbons in Soil by *Medicago sativa* Plant

Ekram Sabah Sahib Al Saidi , Karima F. Abbas, Haider Sajat Hamad,
Mustafa Saddam Muhammad, Abbas Ward Saddam

Department of Environmental health, College of Applied Medical Science, University of Kerbala, Iraq

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Abstract:

Petroleum products are necessary to modern civilization, mostly in the development of economic and agricultural goods. Transporting fuel causes significant environmental risks such as unloading, spills and leaks. For this reason, this study was conducted in order to evaluate and know the possibility of using and applying phytoremediation on soil contaminated with gas oil. This study was taking place at the University of Kerbala. As well as field work was conducted in the college's garden. Twelve pots were used for the phytoremediation of contaminated soil. Each pot, was packed with three kilograms soil garden. All pots were formed concurrently using

1, 3, and 5 g of gas oil per kilogram of soil. Soil with each of the gas oil concentrations was planted with the 50 seeds of selected *Medicago sativa* plant. The control setting was kept without gas oil adding. The experiment lasted about 90 days. It has been determined physical and chemical properties for the soil such as assessment of soil pH, EC, moisture, organic matter; determination of plant properties and estimation removal rat of petroleum hydrocarbon (gas oil). Results showed the highest rate removal 60% was observed within 1g\kg concentration, followed by 3g\kg concentration with removal 39%, where was the lowest removal 14% was shown within 5g\kg concentration. The weight of fresh and dry sample dramatically dropped as the level of contamination raised. The lowest and highest result of the fresh weight test after three months ranged between (1.87 -35.46 gm in 5g\kg concentration and control pots, respectively). The study conclusions that the *Medicago sativa* plant has the ability to tolerate soil contaminated with gas oil, and this plant also provides the appropriate conditions for the analysis of hydrocarbons at all gas oil concentrations.

Keywords: *Hydrocarbons, Medicago sativa, Phytoremediation.*

Introduction

Petroleum, makes a distinguished act in the evolution of contemporary heavy industry and acts as essential resource that civilization depends on, supplying a significant portion of the world's energy (Hassani *et al.*, 2020). Petroleum hydrocarbons are found naturally in the earth in the form of crude oil, coal, and asphalt, and are organic compounds. In addition, petroleum hydrocarbons can be as solids,

liquids, or gases, for instance as natural gas (Kirk, 2005). Hydrogen and carbon create the majority of petroleum hydrocarbons, while nitrogen, sulfur, and oxygen can also be present occasionally. General composition of crude oil (in % mass) as 70-80% carbon, 10-15% hydrogen, 0-10% sulphur, 0-1% nitrogen and 0-5% oxygen (Abdullah *et al.*, 2020).

Petroleum from crude oil can be processed to produce a variety of products, which are then categorized based on their intended usage.

Processed petroleum products, for example heating fuels, kerosene, diesel, and gas oil , involve a complex blend of hydrocarbons (Abdullah *et al.*, 2020; Mohanta *et al.*, 2024). Human activities caused widespread environmental toxins such leaking storage tanks, oil spills, and transportation accidents. Contamination with hydrocarbons may possess a unfavorable effect on the ecosystem and lead to pollution of air, water and soil (Mohanta *et al.*, 2024). Petroleum hydrocarbons are among of the greatest widespread and persistent pollutants in petrochemical-contaminated areas (Ambaye *et al.*, 2023). These pollutant that have been showed to evidence opposite effects to both human and organisms (Viganò *et al.*, 2023).

Furthermore, several investigations conducted globally have shown negative impact petroleum hydrocarbons identified in soil, air and water on human health like including psychological issues, irritation of the respiratory system, skin and renal issues, and blood profile disruption. Additionally , petroleum hydrocarbons' toxicity affects not just human health nevertheless as well as plants, soil microbes, and ecosystem sustainability

(Abdullah *et al.*, 2020) , therefore their control and remediation has become an urgent social and environmental requirement(Viganò *et al.*, 2023).

There are many physical and chemical treatment methods used to limit the spread of hydrocarbon pollutants, but these methods are expensive and require many chemicals and also produce pollutants that harm the environment. On the other hand, phytoremediation use of microorganisms or plants to break down or remove toxins from the soil (Mohanta *et al.*, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2023).It is represented one of the most common treatments, and the most crucial aspect of it is the use of green plants, which not only look good but also have the ability to withstand high concentrations of pollutants, reduce and remove toxins, and stabilize them(Abdullah *et al.*, 2020 ;Hoffman *et al.*, 2019). The goals of this research were to determine the tolerance limits of *Medicago sativa* to gas oil at different concentrations (1, 3, and 5 g/kg) biodegradation of gas oil from soil by the plants and removal rate for each concentration.

Figure 1. The Phytoremediation Study Design

Materials and Methods

Study Design

The research examination performed in the Health Laboratory, Environmental Health Department at the University of Karbala. As well as field work was conducted in the college's garden. The study methodology consists of twelve pots were utilized for phytoremediation treatment of soil contaminated with gas oil. Three replicates for each treatment pot (R1, R2, R3) in addition to the plant control pot (absence of gas oil), Figure 1. The soil was obtained from the garden of Karbala University. Each pot was filled concurrently with 1, 3, and 5 g of gas oil per kilogram of soil. Gas oil was purchased from a nearby gas station. Acetone was used as a solvent and standard gas oil at various quantities in a 50:50 (v/v) ratio. Before planting, the mixture was sprayed onto the garden soil medium, well mixed, and allowed to stand for a week. Each pot holding different concentration of gas oil was filled with fifty seed *Medicago sativa* plants selected. Additionally, water was used to irrigate every experimental plant at a predetermined volume.

Examination Soil's Chemical and Physical Characteristics

We prepared samples of both contaminated and clean soil for conducting tests. The soil was taken and dried at laboratory temperatures. Then a pestle and mortar were used to homogenize the soil. After that, the soil was sieved using a sieve with a diameter of 1.00 mm.

Examination of Electrical Conductivity pH Level, and Soil Moisture Content

Both EC and pH of soil were measured utilizing Estefan(2013) procedure. A glass beaker was filled with 25 g of soil and thoroughly mixed with 25 ml of distilled water by a glass rod. The combination was then allowed to settle for 30 minutes and stirred once more. Next, the electrode of a pH measuring device was placed inside the beaker, and after 30 seconds, a reading was taken and then EC reading was taken. To calculate the soil's moisture content, ten grams

of soil samples were obtained in relation to weight of the dry soil. The percentage of the soil's moisture content was determined (Estefan, 2013).

Examination of Total Organic Carbon

Using incineration process to determined TOC in keeping with (Weaver *et al.*, 1973).

Organic Matter

The following equation was used to estimate the organic matter.

$$\text{Organic matter \%} = \text{total organic carbon} * 1.72$$

Determination of Plant Properties

Plant Lengths and Weight

Plant lengths was estimated through removing and split up the plant pieces from the soil with extreme caution. Following that, plant parts were washed and dried to take out the extra quantity of water. Thereafter, after gathering the plant, the weight in wet state was measured, and afterwards the sample was dried at 75 degrees Celsius for 72 hours at a time to calculate the dry weight.

Total Chlorophyll

To estimate the total chlorophyll in plant leaves, as per (Arnon, 1949) method, (1g) of freshly leaves was crushed with 40 milliliters of acetone at an 80% concentration. It was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 5000 rpm. The process was repeated after transferring the supernatant. In comparison to a blank, the absorbance A was calculated within 645 and 663 nm.

$$\text{Total chlorophyll} = 20.2A_{645} + 8.02A_{663}$$

Evaluation of Petroleum Hydrocarbon

Used Gas Chromatograph to determine the TPH content of the soil samples in keeping with the technique (Chang *et al.*, 1992). The ratio of TPH removal determined by the following , Eq. (1):

$$\% \text{Removal} = \frac{\text{TPH}_0 - \text{TPH}_1}{\text{TPH}_0} * 100$$

Statistical Analysis

The statistical software SPSS version 22 was utilized to determine the data's significance. In order to compensate for experimental errors every experiment was conducted triplicate. One-way ANOVA was used for analyzing the data with a 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results and Discussions

The Soil's Physical and Chemical Characteristics

Before starting the experiment

The properties of the soil were measured before polluting it and before starting the experiment. The soil was free from petroleum hydrocarbons, with good organic content, slightly alkaline pH, and medium electrical conductivity Table 1.

Table1. The Properties of the Soil before Starting the Experiment

PH	EC ms\cm ³	Moisture%	TOC %	Organic matter %
7.6	4.8	4.3 %	4.3%	7.4%

After the experiment is over

The chemical and physical measurements of the soils used in the experiments were submitted after 90 days from the start of the investigation, as demonstrated in figures 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

PH

As appears from the figure 2, PH value in *Medicago sativa* plant between (7.03 -7.3). Plant development is largely affected by pH's

influence on the availability of nutrients (calcium, salt, potassium, and chloride). Both high and low pH produce deficits in critical nutrients that plants need to flourish. The pH of the plant soil in the control pot was more than the pH of the soil in the pots with varying hydrocarbon contents. The outcome accordance with (Abbaspour et al., 2007) was indicated that the organic matter is released hydrogen ion to the soil, which is associated with a decrease in the pH value.

Figure 2. Plant soil PH

Electrical Conductivity

The lowest and highest electrical conductivity in *Medicago sativa* plant rang between (5.1-6.43 mS/cm). The result revealed that the electrical

conductivity of the plant soil in the control pots was fewer than that of the pots with ranging concentrations of gas oil (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Plant Soil Electrical Conductivity

Mahdy.(2011) reported that the organic matter rises the soil's acidity, which leads a decline in the value of pH, which leads to the dissolution of some salts in the soil, thus increasing the value of electrical conductivity. And this was found in this study as there was a relationship between low pH and high electrical conductivity. In addition, Hatami *et al.*(2019) indicated that the addition organic chemicals to the soil has caused an increase in the level of soil salinity.

Moisture

Figure 4 revealed moisture results in *Medicago sativa* plant soil after three months demonstrated the higher percentage in 5g\kg concentration with 10.61 %, followed by 3g\kg concentration with 9.4, followed by 1g\kg concentration, whereas the lowest percentage 6.64% in control pots.

Figure 4. Plant Soil Moisture %

The conducted research by Milala *et al.*(2015) indicate that the roots and pores of plants get coated with hydrocarbons, preventing oxygen and nutrients from freely moving through them. Roots are suffocated, particularly in soils with a soft texture (clay) or shallow soils with a solid subsoil, causing the soil to hold on to water and become more moisture. This results are line with the study carried out by Macoustra *et al.*(2015), where the outcomes of the study were that soils with a high organic content increase the ability of the soil to retain water and prevent evaporation.

Total Organic Carbon

Total organic carbon percentage in *Medicago sativa* plant soil rang between (3.19 %-3.83%) figure 5. The finding indicates that in the pots containing a high concentration of gas oil , the amount of TOC and organic carbon was greater than in the control pots. Macoustra *et al.*(2015) reported that soil contaminated with hydrocarbons contains a higher content of total organic carbon than the content of organic carbon in unpolluted soil.

Figure 5. Total Organic Carbon in *Medicago sativa* Plant Soil

Figure 6. Organic Matter in *Medicago sativa* Plant Soil

Organic Matter

The lowest and highest organic matter ranged between (5.49% -6.6 % in control pot and 5g\kg concentration ,respectively) figure 6. Wang & Liu.(2012) found that high salinity due to high concentrations of hydrocarbons inhibits the activity of microorganisms that decompose organic matter, causing the organic matter to remain in the soil. Another recent study shows injecting the soil with hydrocarbons caused an increase in organic matter (Saraeian *et al.*, 2018).

Plant Properties

Seeds Germination

Figure 7 illustrates how the percentage of seeds that germinated after nine days of being put in treatment pots was determined by comparing the sprouting seedlings with those of the control. The outcome displayed that the highest percentage *Medicago sativa* seed germination was evident in control pots with percentage (44%) followed by 1g\kg concentration with percentage (36%), followed by 3g\kg concentration with percentage (25%), and the lowest percentage (11%) was in 5g\kg concentration. Gas oil endured negative consequences on *Medicago sativa* seed germination. The germination rate of *Medicago sativa* seed drop with the gas oil concentration increasing.

Figure 7. Percentage of Seeds Germination

Lengths of Plants

The results displayed a decrease in lengths of plants growing in soil contaminated with gas oil due to sensitivity to hydrocarbons. Figure 8 represents the maximum inhibition rate in the lengths at concentrations of 5 g/kg and 3 g/kg.

The result of our research is consistent with the result of Visioli *et al.*(2016) reported clear that petroleum hydrocarbons have a severe toxic effect on the length of the roots of plants that grow in contaminated pots, was shorter than the control pots, and it was found that the root lengths is oppositely proportionate to the hydrocarbons concentration . Njoku *et al.*(2009)

found in their studies were that crude oil slows the growth of roots by limiting the amount of

water that may reach the roots and be subsequently absorbed.

Figure 8. Plants Lengths

Total Chlorophyll

Figure 9 shows that a plant grown in soil contaminated with gas oil generally shows a lack

of chlorophyll in the leaves; It decreases with increasing concentration. Chlorophyll in *Medicago sativa* plant between (12.3 mg\gm-30.33mg\gm).

Figure 9. Total Chlorophyll in *Medicago sativa* Plant

That crude oil pollution of soil would limit plant species' ability to synthesize chlorophyll. In the leaves, the total chlorophyll concentration decreased as a result of the alkaline condition generated by the dissolving in cell sap of compounds from oil that were responsible for chlorophyll (Anthony, 2001).

A previous study by Tran *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that the compared a procedure from underground soil contaminated by a crude oil spill, one of which was exposed to an oil spill before forty years in 1975 and the other in 2014, and he used two types of acacia seedlings (*Acacia raddiana* and *Acacia tortilis*) to study their physiological response to the pollutant and their

ability to soil remediation. The results showed, there was a strong decrease the content of chlorophyll in *Acacia raddiana* seedlings grown in contaminated soil.

The Plant Biomass

As seen in figure 10 and 11, Fresh and dry weight lower particular with a higher in the level of gas oil concentration. The lowest and highest result of the fresh weight test after three months ranged between (1.87-35.46 gm in 5g/kg concentration and control pots, respectively). Additionally, the minimum weight of dry plant (0.3 gm) was in 5g/kg concentration and the maximum (7.31 gm) in controls pots.

Figure 10. Wet Weight of *Medicago sativa* Plant

Figure 11. Dry Weight of *Medicago sativa* Plant

The experimental plant demonstrated that afterwards reaper, the biomass was higher in the control pots compared to the pots contaminated with different concentrations of gas oil, where the biomass was lower. The attributed reduced plant growth and inhibition of photosynthesis due to the concentration of gas oil in the soil. The results of present study agreed with studies Cheema *et al.*(2010) where the results of the studies were that hydrocarbon oil reduces the availability of water, oxygen and nutrients in the soil, which leads to reduced growth and a decrease in plant biomass.

The Removal Rate of Gas Oil

As seen in the figure 12 the highest rate removal 60% was observed within 1g/kg concentration, followed by 3g/kg concentration with removal 39%, where was the lowest removal 14% was showed within 5g/kg concentration. The removal rate lowered with a higher concentration of gas oil. The effectiveness of phytoremediation trials was frequently statistically greater compared to the control. Significant impact of research plants on petroleum hydrocarbon elimination at various sampling concentrations $P < 0.05$.

Figure 12. The Removal Rate of Gas Oil

This study proved that hydrocarbons influence plants physiologically and physically alongside to the soil’s chemical and physical characteristics. It was found that the plant can effectively elimination hydrocarbons from the soil at various concentrations.

The percentage of hydrocarbon removal decreases with increasing hydrocarbon concentration, that the removal process occurred in the root zone, where microorganisms in the root zone perform a

symbiotic process with plant roots, the root secretions are an important and influential factor in the gathering of microorganisms. In the root zone, that radicals secrete compounds that can be broken down into soluble and insoluble in water, low molecular weight carbohydrates, amino acids, organic ions, secondary metabolites, and organic polymers constitute soluble substances all of these compounds and organic carbon are used to provide energy for microorganisms in the soil, plants can tolerate organic pollutants (Saracian *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 13. Removal Efficiency between the Treatment

Conclusions

1. The findings of the study illustrated that the *Medicago sativa* plant has the ability to survive and tolerate soil contaminated with gas oil after 90 days.
2. The removal rate lowered with a higher concentration of hydrocarbons. The highest rate removal was observed within 1g\kg and 3g\kg concentration.
3. Seed germination, Total chlorophyll, plant biomass and lengths of plants decreased with the increasing gas oil concentration.

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